

Natural Dairy Farming - A New Trend in the Dairy Sector

K. Santhosh

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ABSTRACT

Natural Dairy cultivating implies raising creatures on natural feed (for example pastures developed without the utilization of chemical fertilizer or pesticides), approaching the field or outside, alongside the limited use of anti-microbials and chemicals. Items acquired from Organic dairy ranch are natural dairy items. Natural cultivating is an arrangement of creation, a bunch of objective-based guidelines that permit ranchers to deal with their specific circumstances independently while keeping up with natural honesty. This article highlighted, the advantages, conditions required, imperatives included and managerial practices of natural dairying, alongside data about the administrative specialists worried about the natural dairy cultivating, were inspected momentarily to make understudies and ranchers mindful of natural dairy cultivating.

Key words: Eco-friendly dairy cultivating, Natural dairy, Organic milk.

Natural development is based on a crucial rule, sound soils lead to solid harvests, sound creatures, sound people and a solid planet. Natural yield and animals creation centers around building soil natural matter and science to make an economical, unique climate for delivering good food and feed. The natural cultivating development is regularly consented to have started during the 1940s in England with the works of Sir Albert Howard, who found out with regards to natural practices in India during the 1920s (APEDA, 2014). The explanations behind delivering and buying natural food are individual just as intricate. Nonetheless, most will fall into three classifications *i.e.*, wellbeing, local area and climate. There has been a developing worry about the ordinary dairy structure worldview that depends on manufactured contributions to expand yields; presents dangers to the climate and wellbeing.

The idea of organic dairy framing is a relative newbie. When contrasted with natural products, vegetables, grains and some domesticated animals have for some time been backbones of natural development. Natural dairy flooded into the natural commercial center during the 1990s, setting up a good foundation for itself as a significant classification (Christine, 2009).

The accomplishment of natural dairy can to a great extent be credited to a few basic occasions, including expanded buyer mindfulness about hereditarily adjusted corn, soybean and different yields treated with a variety of engineered pesticides being taken care of to animals, the taking care of butcher results to ruminants and worries about frantic cow sickness and the expanded utilization of manufactured drugs including chemicals, anti-toxins and steroids-have urged numerous purchasers to look for natural dairy items. These shoppers have come to depend on the confirmations of guaranteed natural dairy as a confided in the wellspring of pure dairy items.

Natural dairy products are frequently seen as "Door Products", in that customers will make their initial introductions to natural buying by purchasing natural dairy products, at

Department of Agriculture Engineering, Bannari Amman Institute of Technology, Sathyamangalam, Erode-638 401, Tamil Nadu, India.

Corresponding Author: K. Santhosh, Department of Agriculture Engineering, Bannari Amman Institute of Technology, Sathyamangalam, Erode-638 401, Tamil Nadu, India.

Email: santhosh.ag19@bitsathy.ac.in

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last expanding their faithfulness to natural items as they become progressively food shrewd (Dhiman *et al.*, 1999).

Characterizing organic dairy

Natural dairy cultivating implies raising creatures on natural feed (for example pastures developed without the utilization of manures or pesticides), approaching the field or outside, alongside the limited use of anti-microbials and chemicals. Items got from organic dairy ranch are natural dairy items. Natural dairy cultivating is an arrangement of creation, a bunch of objective-based guidelines that permit ranchers to deal with their specific circumstances separately while keeping up with natural respectability.

The executives

Natural makers of domesticated animals items should not keep illness treatment to address the domesticated animals item as natural. An appropriate crowd wellbeing project ought to incorporate procedures for illness counteraction, parasitic control and sickness therapy. All immunizations for endemic illnesses are endorsed. Locally available homegrown, naturopathic, homeopathic medicines are endorsed for use on natural creatures. Anti-toxin usage is confined to 30 days or double the named season of with drone period. The utilization of chemicals was completely confined. Sterilization practices such as teat plunge, draining disinfection

synthetics, etc. are permitted. Notwithstanding, hardware should be twofold washed with clear (tried) water preceding draining.

In a natural dairy ranch (Greene and Dimitri, 2003)

- Cows and calves are taken care of 100 per cent natural feed.
- Natural yields, roughage and field are developed without the utilization of manufactured composts and pesticides that poor people have been painstakingly screened and supported for natural use.
- Land used to develop natural yields should be liberated from all denied materials for no less than three (3) years before the principal natural collection.
- Non-regular feed added substances and enhancements, for example, nutrients and minerals should likewise be endorsed for use.
- Hereditarily altered creatures (GMOs, called "Barred Methods" in the guideline) are prohibited.
- Engineered milk replacers are precluded. Calves should be benefited from natural milk as it were.
- All creatures should approach the outside (in light of climate conditions). Creatures north of a half-year-old enough should approach the field during the developing season.
- Limited utilization of anti-toxins (possibly utilized when cows are sick). Just endorsed medical services items can be utilized.
- Natural creatures may not be taken care of ANY butcher results, urea, or compost.
- The government assistance of the creatures should be taken care of Certain methodology, for example, tail docking are disallowed. Different strategies, such as dehorning, should be done as such as to limit the pressure on the creature.
- A natural rancher should keep adequate records to check their consistency with the principles.
- Each ranch is examined and evaluated each year. Any ranch can be reviewed unannounced whenever.

Natural dairy products

Natural dairy products should be from creatures that have been under nonstop natural administration for something like one year preceding the development of the milk or milk items.

Prevalence as far as nature of items

Natural Milk is better for Health. Milk is an ideal pointer that mirrors the degree of toxins and pesticides those debased dairy cows and just as dairy. Assortment of dairy items, for example, margarine, spread oil, margarine milk, cheddar, yogurt, entire milk, skimmed milk powder, ghee and frozen yogurt are utilized in our day to day routine eating regimen. Of which milk shares a huge part. Traditional milk might contain deposits of chemicals utilized on the dairy creatures (for abundance milk creation), pesticides, anti-microbial, urea and solvents which truly affect the singular's wellbeing. In regular dairy homesteads, such practices were normal to get more milk past their inherent limitations. Improper protein is taken care of to cows for animating the quick development or milk creation. This large number of variables make

ordinary milk mediocre in quality. Utilization of such milk might prompt early pubescence, touchiness, hormonal lopsidedness and particular sorts of malignant growth in people (Hallam, 2003; Heckman, 2006). Milk from natural and non-natural dairies is having contrast however natural milk is far better than non-natural milk.

Some distinctions make natural milk predominant pointed out as under:

CLA

Milk contains Conjugated Linoleic Acid (CLA). The capacity of CLA in the human body is to help invulnerable framework and lessen the development of growths. CLA levels in natural milk are higher because these cows eat more prominent measures of natural grass, feed and silage (McBride, 2010).

Pesticides

Organic dairy ranches don't utilize any fake pesticides on pastures where cows eat. While on customary dairy cultivates very nearly 500 pesticides are utilized on the fields. The primary issue with the pesticides besides their singular harmfulness is that each examination shows how these synthetic substances respond when consolidated, in the mixed drink impact. It has more effects on the youngsters because of their youthful organs and safe frameworks.

Anti-toxins

On regular dairy ranches, cows are given anti-toxins regularly to forestall sickness and contamination. While on natural dairy cultivates first normal cures are utilized for cow's ailment, on the off chance that it won't work then anti-toxins are given. At the point when natural cow should be treated with anti-microbials then the 'withdrawal period' is impressively longer than that suggested for customary cultivating.

GMOs and solvents

The feed given to cows on natural dairy ranches is liberated from GMOs (Genetically adjusted organic entities), dissolvable concentrates and urea. So, it brings about milk that is liberated from these substances.

Chemicals

Fertility chemicals are utilized regularly in ordinary dairy homesteads to guarantee that calves are imagined and brought into the world inside characterized administration time frames and to synchronize clusters of cows or yearlings to calve around a similar time. Chemicals like rBGH (Recombinant Bovine Growth Hormone) and Oxytocin were frequently used to expand milk creation and cause simple disappointment of milk individually. While on natural dairy ranches, utilization of chemicals should be completely restricted.

Controlling specialists

US Department of Agriculture (USDA) sent off National Organic Program (NOP) in October 2002, a power to manage and synchronize natural creation, cultivating and showcasing in the United States. Presently, all items sold as "Natural" in the U.S. should be delivered, dealt with and

handled by a solitary standard-the NOP "Last Rule" (USDA, 2000) (Moschos and Mantzoros, 2002).

In India, The National Program on Organic Production (NPOP) [under The Agricultural and Processed Food Products Export Development Authority (APEDA)] was formally sent off in 2000 and advised under FTDR (Foreign Trade Development and Regulation) act in the year 2001. The NPOP was agreed with equivalency by the European Union for its guideline on Organic Agriculture EC 2092/91 (USDA, 2000). That implies that any item ensured by NPOP can have prepared admittance to European business sectors without the requirement for discrete EU (European Union) Certification. The USDA has likewise perceived the certification framework taken on by India under NPOP (USDA, 2000).

The National Program for Organic Production (NPOP) proposes to give an institutional component to the execution of National Standards for Organic Production, through a National Accreditation Policy and Program. The point of the National Program for natural creation is:

- (a) To give the method for assessment of affirmation programs for natural horticulture and items according to the supported standards.
- (b) To authorize certificate programs.
- (c) Certification of natural items in adjustment to the National Standards for Organic Products.
- (d) To empower the improvement of natural cultivating and natural handling.

Imperatives for organic dairy farming in India

The natural dairy area keeps on being a quickly developing fragment. To meet all requirements for the natural name, natural ranchers are denied from utilizing manufactured development chemicals (rBGH), hereditarily designed living beings, anti-microbials and harmful, diligent and engineered pesticides. The norms additionally command a thorough framework for examination, affirmation and check of natural practices, all of which secure customers who pick natural items. The future difficulties are to keep supplies following request and to bring down the expenses looked at by natural ranchers (Pierce and Tilth, 2009).

Challenges

Natural dairy ranchers considered the most troublesome parts of natural milk creation are the,

1. Certification administrative work and consistency cost was the most difficult.
2. Sourcing natural information sources, including grains and scavenges, feed supplements and replacement of yearlings.
3. High expenses of creation and keeping up with creature wellbeing.
4. Others (for example-regular catastrophes, for example, dry spells, floods and so forth).

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